

1 **Genes associated with fibrotic or stenotic Crohn's Disease in humans.**

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7 We utilized whole transcriptome technology to identify in an unbiased fashion genes that
8 describe or define the fibrotic or stenotic B2 phenotype in humans with Crohn's Disease.

9 We recently described discovery research aimed at delineating molecular mechanisms
10 underlying the penetrating or fistulizing B3 phenotype, discovering a multitude of significant
11 changes in the penetrating/fistulizing phenotype transcriptome including keratin family silencing,
12 coenzyme and NADP oxidase expression changes with similarity to chronic granulomatous
13 disease (wherein mutation of a phox NADPH oxidase gene results in fistulizing immune disease)
14 as well as specific activation of a TCF/Lef factor, TCF21, revealing a nuclear effector that
15 specifies a developmental origin that features the aggressive penetrative phenotype. TCF
16 developmental origin of a subtype, keratin family silencing within the context of epithelial integrity
17 compromise, and dysregulation of ATP metabolic and oxidoreductive functions through
18 regulation of coenzyme, NADP+ oxidase and ubiquinol-associated genes were only a few of the
19 cellular processes in a system containing a collection of genes with potential to confer
20 penetrative function in an inflammatory bowel disease.

21 We continued here discovery of B2-specific subtype genes of using RNA-sequencing of the
22 terminal ileum in a pediatric Crohn's Disease cohort with B1 or B2 disease.
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28

Results

We performed an expression screen using the human cells and tissues to identify genes important for the fibrotic/stenotic (Montreal B2) Crohn's Disease phenotype.

1. Cross linking potential: TKT transkeletose
2. Glutaminase
 - a. GlS2 was a CD common gene
3. Transglutaminase
 - a. Tgm1 was a B2 enriched gene
4. Clotting cascade
 - a. F8 family
 - b. F12
 - c. Pafahb3
 - d. Vwf1
5. Peptides and other molecules with structural, support or interaction based functions rich in Glutamine
 - a. Qpctl
 - b. CCER2
 - c. FPGS
 - d. PGPEP
 - e. Ggtlc3 and Dglucy2 were CD common genes
6. Collagen
 - a. Col14a1
 - b. PLOD1
 - c. Plod3
 - d. Pcolce2
 - e. Col17a1
 - f. Col18a1
7. Fibrinogen-type
 - a. Fbrsl1
 - b. Fmod
 - c. Fbrsl1
8. TNF superfamily
 - a. Tnfsf9
 - b. Tnfsf12
 - c. TNFRSF13b
 - d. Tnfaip8l1
9. Clec receptors
 - a. Clec11a
 - b. Clec4d

- 1 10. Cell death
- 2 a. BIRC2 silencing
- 3 b. BAIAP2 modest B2 enrichment
- 4 c. Bax
- 5 d. Bcor1
- 6 e. Ldhd
- 7 11. Regeneration: cartilage type
- 8 a. CTHRC1
- 9 12. Energy: mTOR, PI3-K and AKT
- 10 a. Mlst8
- 11 b. Rptor
- 12 c. Akt1
- 13 d. Akt1s1
- 14 e. Rictor1 was depleted in B2
- 15 f. Pik3r2
- 16 g. Pik3ca was depleted in B2 and pik3cd was B1/B2 common
- 17 13. Ceramide
- 18 a. Ctp
- 19 b. Gba1
- 20 c. CER1 deficient
- 21 14. Cell division (asymmetric versus symmetric) program
- 22 a. Aph1a
- 23 b. Poc1b silencing
- 24 c. Mon1a
- 25 15. Keratins
- 26 a. Krt8
- 27 b. Krt18
- 28 c. Krt19
- d. Tchp induction was modest
16. Morphogens
- a. Bmp1
- b. Wnt5b
17. Matrix metalloproteinases and ECM
- a. Mmp23a
- b. Mmp23b
- c. Mmp7
- d. Mmp14
- e. Adamts7
18. Axin
- a. Axin1
19. Epoxide
- a. Ephx1 was B2 specific
- b. Ephx2 was B1/B2 common

- 1 20. Butyrophilin
- 2 a. BTN2A1/2 and BTNL8 were B1/B2 common
- 3 21. CxxC
- 4 a. Cript depletion
- 5 b. CXXC1
- 6 22. Guidance molecules
- 7 a. RGMA
- 8 b. Slit1
- 9 c. Sema4b
- 10 d. Sema5b
- 11 23. Enteral (GI) nervous system, neuroactive molecules and neuropeptides involved in GI
- 12 related functions (feeding, satiety, hunger, peristalsis, emptying, etc.)
- 13 a. GIPR
- 14 24. Hypoxia
- 15 a. EglN2 and EglN-3 were B2 enriched
- 16 25. Sulfate
- 17 a. Hspg2
- 18 b. Hs6st1
- 19 c. Sulf2
- 20 26. cAMP and related second messenger type signaling with physiologic relation (adenosine,
- 21 ADCY, PDE, etc)
- 22 a. Pde4a
- 23 b. Creb3l1
- 24 c. Ampd2
- 25 d. Adat3
- 26 e. Adora1
- 27 f. Gpr135
- 28 g. Gpr108
- 29 27. Junctional
- 30 a. Jsrb1
- 31 b. Jup
- 32 c. Ajm1
- 33 d. Pkp3
- 34 e. Aqp10
- 35 f. Env1
- 36 28. Cytoskeletal (actin and tubulin)
- 37 a. Capzb
- 38 b. Capg
- 39 c. Profilin
- 40 d. Gelsolin
- 41 e. Cofilin
- 42 f. Talin 1
- 43 g. Actin

- 1 29. Glycogen associated
- 2 a. Gys1
- 3 b. Pygb
- 4 30. Stenotic enriched cytokines and interleukins
- 5 a. Il17ra
- 6 b. Il2rg and IL34 were modestly enriched in B2
- 7 31. Chemokines
- 8 a. Xcl1 and xcl2 were depleted in the B2 subtype
- 9 b. Cxcl16 and ccl22 were weakly B2 enriched
- 10 c. Cxcl10 and ccl8 were depleted in B2.
- 11 32. Growth factor signaling
- 12 a. Igf2 and Igf2r
- 13 b. Hgh1
- 14 c. Pgf
- 15 d. FGF2 and FGF11 were B1/B2
- 16 33. Kinesins
- 17 a. Kif26a was B2 specific
- 18 34. Geranyl geranylation
- 19 a. Rabggta was B2 enriched
- 20 b. Pgg1b was B2 silenced
- 21 35. Secondary lymphoid organ associated
- 22 a. Fdcsp was B1/B2 common
- 23 b. Lyve1 repression
- 24 c. Eola2 induction
- 25 36. B-cell program genes
- 26 a. AICDA was B1/B2 common
- 27 37. Killer cell (NK) cytotoxicity or errors in self recognition
- 28 a. All KLR receptors were depleted in B2 including
 - i. Klrc2
 - ii. Klrd1
 - iii. Klrf1
 - iv. Klrk1
 - v. Klrc3
 - vi. Klrc4
- b. NKG7 was B1/B2 common
38. Cytotoxicity and immune effector function related
 - i. Granulin was B2 enriched
39. Filaments
- a. Flna
- b. Flnc
40. Saccharide biosynthetic and associated
- a. Sccpdh and pbdc1 were B1/B2 common

- 1 41. Carbohydrate biology
- 2 a. Chst14 and chst3 enriched in B2
- 3 42. Glycolytic function
- 4 a. Pfk1
- 5 b. G6pc3
- 6 c. Pgls
- 7 d. Gdpgp1
- 8 e. PgD
- 9
- 10 43. Amyloidogenic molecules and signaling
- 11 a. APP
- 12 b. APPB1
- 13 c. Notch3
- 14 d. Jag2
- 15 e. Apobr
- 16 f. Apol1
- 17 g. Prnp
- 18
- 19 44. Organelles with cargos of cross linking potential: Golgi function
- 20 a. Garin5a
- 21 b. Ergic3
- 22 c. Sys1
- 23 d. Fam20c
- 24 e. Bet1L
- 25 f. Cog8
- 26 g. Tango2
- 27 45. Organelles with cargos of cross linking potential: Peroxisome function
- 28 a. Prxl2b
- 29 b. Pex5 was B1/B2 common
- 30 c. Pex1 was depleted in B2
- 31 d. Pex12 was weakly B2 enriched
- 32 e. Pxdn was B1/B2 common
- 33 46. Organelles with cargos of cross linking potential: lysosome function
- 34 a. Bloc1s3
- 35 b. Hps1
- 36 c. Spns1
- 37 d. Lamp1
- 38 e. Hps
- 39 f. Cln3
- 40 g. Lypla2
- 41 47. ATP and the mitochondria
- 42 a. Ndufs7
- 43 b. Ndufs8
- 44 c. Ndufv1
- 45 d. Ndufa11
- 46 e. Atp6v0c
- 47 f. Atp1b2

- 1 g. Atp5f1
- 2 h. Ruvbl2
- 3 i. Atp6ap1
- 4 j. Nqo1

48. Tcf25 identifies the stenotic-fibrotic B2 phenotype in the terminal ileum.

- 5 a. Tcf4, Tcf7L2 and TCF19 were B1/B2 common
- 6 b. Tle3 and Tle5 were enriched in B2 in the terminal ileum
- 7 c. PPARD was B2 specific
- 8 d. PPARA was B1/B2 common

49. Immune receptor profile in B2 terminal ileum

- 9 a. Vsig1, Amigo3 and Lingo1 were B2 specific
- 10 b. MS4A4A, MS4A6A, Ms4A7 and Ms4AE were silenced in B2

50. Lymphocyte antigen and blood group antigens

- 11 a. Hcg27 was silenced
- 12 b. Ly6g5c was weakly B2 enriched
- 13 c. Thy-1 was B2 enriched
- 14 d. Stag1/2 were depleted in B2

51. The epithelial mesenchymal transition program and changes in cell polarity

- 15 a. Col1a1
- 16 b. Col1a2
- 17 c. Vim1
- 18 d. Vim1-as1
- 19 e. Scrib1
- 20 f. Dvl3
- 21 g. Pard6a
- 22 h. Rhbdd2 and Rhbdd3 were B2 specific
- 23 i. Rhbd1/2 was B1/B2 common

52. Sphingomyelin biochemistry

- 24 a. Smpdl3b
- 25 b. Smpd1
- 26 c. Smpd2
- 27 d. S1PR1 and S1PR2 were B1/B2 common

53. Autophagy

- 28 a. Atg2a
- b. Atg4d
- c. Sqstm1

- 1 54. Ubiquitin and proteasomal machinery
- 2 a. Adrm1
- 3 b. Wwp2
- 4 c. Ube2o
- 5 d. Urm1
- 6 e. Mindy4
- 7 f. Usp22
- 8 g. Ube2m
- 9 h. Usp4
- 10 i. Ubqln4
- 11 j. Ubn1
- 12 k. PSMG3
- 13 l. Psmc4
- 14 55. Granuloma associated
- 15 a. CLPP
- 16 b. Mif
- 17 c. Maea
- 18 56. Podocyte
- 19 a. Podnl
- 20 b. Podn
- 21 c. Synpo
- 22 d. Podxl2
- 23 57. Fibroblast biology
- 24 a. Fgfbp1
- 25 b. Fgfbp3 was silenced
- 26 58. ER stress, protein synthesis quality control and unfolded protein response
- 27 a. Atf4 modest B2 enrichment with Atf6 and Atf2b depletion
- 28 b. OS9
- c. Erp29
- d. Ergic
- e. Ern2
- f. Ssr4
- g. Srpra
- h. Kdelr1
- i. Ugt2b15 and Ugt2b17 were modestly B2 enriched
- j. Mgat1 and Mgat2 were B2 enriched
59. Interferon in the B2 phenotype
- a. Ifitm10 was B2 specific
- b. Irgq was B2 specific
- c. Ifit3 and Ifit5, IFI16, IFITM1 were all silenced in B2
- d. Irf2bp1
- e. Irf3 was enriched in B2
- f. Irf2 and IRF6 were B1/B2 common in the terminal ileum

- 1 60. Isomerases
- 2 a. Pin4, ppil1, ppih, pdia2 and mpi were B1/B2 common
- 3 61. Proteases and peptidases
- 4 a. Capn1: calpain1
- 5 b. Htra1
- 6 c. Timp2
- 7 d. Rnpepl1
- 8 e. Ctsz
- 9 f. Ctsd
- 10 g. Ctsw
- 11 h. Ctsa
- 12 i. CpZ was B2 specific
- 13 j. Cpe was B1/B2 shared
- 14 62. Superoxide
- 15 a. Sod3
- 16 63. Kidney-expressed genes
- 17 a. Polycystic: pkd1l1 silencing
- 18 b. Nephronectin-type: nphp4
- 19 c. Tubular interstitial: tinagl1
- 20 d. Cstb and Cst3
- 21 64. Aldehyde enzymatic function
- 22 a. Aldh4a1
- 23 b. Aldh16a1
- 24 65. Peptides and peptide associated genes of interest
- 25 a. ACEH
- 26 b. SGTA
- 27 66. Mannose biochemistry
- 28 a. ALG1
- b. MOGS
67. Aldolases
- a. Taldo1
- b. Aldoa
68. Nicotinamide signaling
- a. Sirt5 and Sirt6 were modestly enriched in the B2 subtype
- b. NMNAT and naprt were modestly B2 enriched
69. Aging and rejuvenation
- a. Mboat7 was B2 specific
- b. Mboat2 was B1/B2 common
- c. Paqr6 and Paqr8 were shared
- d. Paqr3 was suppressed in B2 phenotype

- 1 70. Heme and iron
- 2 a. TFR2
- 3 b. Hmox2
- 4 c. Fth1
- 5 d. Ciao2a was depleted in B2 as was Isca
- 6 71. Oxidoreductive
- 7 a. Ogfod3 and OGFOD2 were B2 specific
- 8 b. Ogfod1 was B1/B2 common
- 9 c. Noxo1
- 10 72. Cell adhesion
- 11 a. Icam4
- 12 b. Cercam
- 13 c. Nectin1
- 14 d. Madcam1
- 15 e. Boc
- 16 f. Bcam
- 17 g. Biglycan
- 18 h. Dag1
- 19 73. Cholesterol
- 20 a. Ebp
- 21 b. DHCR7 and DHCR24 were B2 enriched significantly or modestly
- 22 c. Ldlrad was b2 enriched
- 23 74. Fatty acids
- 24 a. FA2H
- 25 b. Fasn
- 26 c. Ffar4
- 27 d. FAAH and Faah2 were B1/B2 common
- 28 e. AADAC was also B1/B2 common
75. Short and long_chain hydrocarbon
- a. Acox3
76. Spink and KLK
- a. Spink5
- b. Klk1 was weakly B2 enriched
- c. Klk10, Klk11 and Klk13 were B1/B2 common
77. Scavenger and cysteine-rich
- a. Ssc5d
- b. Scamp3
- c. Scamp4
78. Chitin related
- a. Biotinidase was B1/B2 shared
- b. ALG1
- c. Alg12
- d. Chid1

- 1 79. Other enzymes and genes
- 2 a. Gcdh
- 3 b. Aasdhppt deficiency
- 4 c. Glo1 deficiency
- 5 d. Periaxin was common
- 6 e. Ladinin
- 7 f. Ncln
- 8 g. Endog
- 9 h. Comt
- 10 i. Txlna
- 11 j. Accs depletion
- 12 k. Lct depletion
- 13 80. Transgelin, nidogen, and other wound and regeneration
- 14 a. Tagln2
- 15 b. Tagln
- 16 c. Nid2
- 17 d. EREG suppression
- 18 81. Cyclooxygenase
- 19 a. Cox2
- 20 b. Cox3; both were enriched to varying degree in B2
- 21 82. Potential folate biosynthesis changes
- 22 a. MTHFD2L deficiency
- 23 b. MTRR deficiency
- 24 c. FOLH1 and FOLH1B were shared
- 25 83. Cytochrome
- 26 a. Cyb5r3
- 27 b. Cyb5r1
- 28 c. Cyb561
- d. Cyba
- e. Cyb561d2
- f. Cyp2s1
- g. Cyp2c8 was deleted in B2
- h. Cyp2j2 and Cyp4f12 were B1/B2 common, as were Cybb, Cyb5 and Cyb5a

1 **Discussion**

2 We identified here using transcriptome-based expression screening of primary tissues from
3 humans with Crohn's Disease dozens of genes that are activated or repressed in the
4 gastrointestinal tract of humans with fibrotic/stenotic Crohn's Disease.

5 Functional analysis in animal models or intestine organoid culture with systematic depletion and
6 over-expression may provide insight into molecular mechanisms and provide data supporting a
7 model of disease phenotype with multiple genetic contributions, each distinguishable and with
varying degree of influence on the fibrotic phenotype.

8 We use next generation technologies and computational, quantitative methods to describe the
9 molecular signature of human disease: to understand the molecular basis of human disease, to
10 support the scientific and medical community and to support discovery and development of
11 drugs for treatment of IBD through mechanism-based target identification. We study Crohn's
12 Disease using transcriptomic and proteomic methods to describe the gene signature of a human
13 disease that features an early- and very early-onset population, is associated with resistance to
14 clinical intervention, most specifically morbidity relating to the stenotic and penetrating subtypes
(B2 and B3). We use Crohn's Disease as a model for complex genetic disease.

15 Identification of the major IBD susceptibility loci through mapping efforts (e.g., lineage
16 disequilibrium), GWAS identification of variants in the leucine rich region of NOD2, the IBD locus
17 with highest genetic contribution to IBD, as well as advances in clinical management of IBD
18 including the introduction of sulfasalazine-derived mesalamine for eicosanoid-targeted treatment
19 of inflammation in the gut for mild to moderate disease, small molecule inhibitors of the Janus
20 kinase JAK signaling pathway, and biologics that target TNF-alpha, integrins that target gut
21 lymphatic intravasation, as well as immunoglobulin and immunoglobulin-like agents that
22 neutralize or target cytokines, cytokine subunits and genes that encode receptor subunits for the
interleukin-23 and interleukin-17 pathways, for moderate and severe disease, have all occurred
within the last three decades. Continued study of penetrating and fibrotic stenotic IBD is required
to establish protocols that facilitate complete response in a patient population prone to relapse.
Stricture that prohibits feeding and intake of liquids is a medical emergency; small bowel
structure will not accommodate nasogastric and gastric access points, and long term intravenous
total parental nutrition places the patient at risk, separate from quality of life considerations, for
liver failure resulting from extended TPN.